

A Documentation of Traditional Knowledge of Water Management Mechanism Thematic Area: Traditional Arts, Crafts, and Cultural Preservation

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Historically it was often observed that there was an intricate system of appropriate preservation and utilization of necessary natural resources in society. Particularly in temples or establishments with large population, maintaining proper water supply was compulsorily essential. In this context it may be highlighted that a comprehensive water management system including collection, storage and purification, was built in the palace of Jahajmahal, Mandu at Madhya Pradesh. The palace was constructed by Ghiyathuddin Khilji (1469-1501) which included a large Harem, to house about 15000 women.

The palace was built on a narrow strip of land between two lakes Munj and Kapur Talaos. The building was 110 metre long, 15 metre wide and 9.7 metre tall. A huge quantity of rain water collected on the roof of this rectangular building ran down from a height of 9.7 metres opening into a natural fountain. Junk particles of various sizes were naturally filtered while the water passed in tremendous force through a narrow channel to form a fountain. The filtered water then gradually flowed through another channel and was stored in Kapur Talao. From there it again streamed into a pit area divided into various compartments segregated for purification. Each of the chambers were filled with lime, charcoal, sand, alum and other herbs respectively and the water slowly passed through these chambers serially, in a regulated method. The water flow was controlled by arranging the pits, with gradual slants, while the water flowed from one pit to another through narrow holes at different levels. This medieval system of water purification has a close resemblance to our modern Reverse Osmosis system.

Keywords: Traditional Knowledge, water management, cultural heritage, Jahaj Mahal, Mandu.